

Holocene background concentrations and actual enrichment factors of metals in sediments from Ria Formosa, Portugal.

Abstract

Metal history in a natural system was described since the early Holocene by analysing the preserved subsurface sediment record and present-day surface sediments. Normalized geochemical data from six sediment cores (129 samples) was compared with 28 surface samples. Pre-anthropogenic sedimentary environments allowed the definition of local natural Background Values. Enrichment Factors were then used for elements discrimination in terms of natural and anthropogenic inputs to the system. While subsurface results displayed a similar behaviour in all cores, pointing to largely undisturbed system, surface sediments show significant contamination, with high enrichment factors for As, Cu, Pb, and Zn. Other metal pollutants have generally low enrichment values, suggesting natural conditions. Surface results were reproduced as metal enrichment maps which evidenced anthropogenic sources in specific locations. This work reveals the importance of combining subsurface and surface geochemical data with mapping techniques in order to better evaluate the environmental quality of a natural system.

Keywords: Geochemistry; Metal contamination; Sediments; Anthropogenic sources; GIS-analysis; Ria Formosa

1. Introduction

Estuarine and coastal environments can be enriched in trace metals through river discharges (Martin and Whitfield, 1983), atmospheric transport (Martin et al., 1989), and anthropogenic sources (Cotté-Krief et al., 2000). In the water column metals adsorb to fine particulate suspended matter and settle on with sediments. Metal enriched particles are thus accumulated in the sedimentary record through the millennia. The analysis of the preserved sediment record combined with radiometric dating techniques (e.g. ^{210}Pb and ^{137}Cs) can provide an evolution perspective of metal contaminants in a system at historical time scales (for a broader discussion see Heim and Schwarzbauer, 2013). For larger time periods, namely pre-anthropogenic natural metal concentrations, ^{14}C dated sediments techniques could deliver information that allows to infer the beginning of the anthropogenic influence (e.g. Shotyk et al., 1998; Delgado et al., 2008), and as such determining a more complete record of the metal contamination evolution in a specific area (e.g. Delgado et al., 2012).

Determination of natural, region specific Background Value (Bkd) from the pre-anthropogenic part of the sedimentary record is a favourable approach in order to assess the human impact of metal contamination in coastal systems (Mil-Homens et al., 2006). It could be particularly useful in the sediment quality assessment of the estuarine systems (Delgado, et al., 2010). Bkd could be used to determine the status and degree of environmental contamination through a use of the Enrichment Factors (EF) (Feng et al., 2004).

The use of single reference background such as average shale (Turekian and Wedephol, 1961), Upper Crust average values (Taylor and McLennan, 1985), the average composition of the surficial rocks exposed to weathering (Martin and Meybeck, 1979) or regional geochemical baseline obtained from extensive regional database of sediment metal concentrations if available (Alexander et al., 1993) are common approaches applied previously for determination of metal EF for the Portuguese continental shelf sediments (Mil-Homens et al., 2006; Mil-Homens et al., 2007; Martins et al., 2012). However, as the geology of coastal systems differs from study site to study site, this approach could be misleading and the use of pre-industrial values to assess anthropogenic input would be preferred (Mil-Homens et al., 2006). Several authors have determined the site-specific Bkd for coastal systems (Fernández-Caliani et al. 1997; Borrego et al., 2002; Ligeró et al., 2002; Santos-Bermejo et al., 2003; Delgado et al., 2008) that were then used in their sediment and environmental quality assessment (Blasco et al. 2010, Delgado et al., 2010).

Several studies have investigated surface metal concentration levels in the Ria Formosa in the last three decades (Benoliel et al., 1988, Blasco et al., 2010; Cortesão et al., 1986; Silva et al., 2013). Moreover, from 1981 to 2010 the National Portuguese Hydrographic Institute has carried out metal contamination monitoring program in which covered 10 surface sampling stations situated in the Ria Formosa lagoon (Valença et al., 2012). However, to the best of our knowledge, none of the previous works focused on the determination of its metal Bkd. The preserved Holocene Ria Formosa palaeoenvironmental sedimentary record (Sousa et al., 2018) provides an excellent opportunity to determine the Ria Formosa Bkd. This information is complementary to the existing reconstruction of environmental change in Ria Formosa Barrier Island System during the Holocene, as proposed by Sousa et al. (2018), identifying as such the pre-anthropogenic conditions and hence the local Bkd values.

From a geochemical perspective, our goal is to establish the local Bkd for contaminant elements in Ria Formosa and discriminate between natural and anthropogenic inputs of these elements into the system. Moreover, through the geochemical characterization of surface sediments, including metal contamination levels, it is possible to better assess and locate the actual anthropogenic sources of metal contaminants in this coastal environment. As a first study that uses the Ria

Formosa specific Bkd, this work aims to calculate metal EF and represent present-day metal contamination levels in the lagoon in the form of metal enrichment maps and present distribution created with the assistance of a Geographical Information System (GIS).

2. Regional setting

The Ria Formosa is a barrier island system with a costal lagoon enclosed behind a sequence of five barrier islands and two spits, extending nearly 55km. Two of its six tidal inlets were artificially opened and stabilized during the 20th century (Ferreira et al., 2016). Intertidal features of the Ria Formosa system represent almost 90% of its total area, where only 14% is permanently flooded (Andrade et al., 2004). Large salt marshes, sand muddy flats and a complex channels network are its predominating geomorphological features. Tidal regime is almost macrotidal, (maximum tidal range of 3.5m), semidiurnal, with a range between an average of 2.8m and 1.3m for spring and neap tides respectively (Pacheco et al., 2008). Land reclamation since the beginning of the 20th century modified extensively the configuration of the coastal lagoon (Arnaud-Fassetta et al., 2006; Sousa et al., 2019). Its origin is related to the early to mid-Holocene deceleration of sea level rise following the Last Glacial Maximum, reaching a dynamic equilibrium and a geomorphological configuration similar to present in the last 3000 years BP (Sousa et al., 2018). The continental bordering unit is composed mainly by Plio-Pleistocene red clayey sands with rounded pebbles of quartz and iron nodules (Moura and Boski, 1999) and Jurassic to Miocene limestone, silts, marls and beach rock (Chester, 2012), cut through several tributaries' valleys. The Ria Formosa is also of great socio-economic and environmental importance, with a Natural Park status since 1987, and recognized as an important wetland at European and International level as a Natura 2000 and Ramsar site (e.g. Sousa et al., 2019).

3. Materials and Methods

3.1 Sampling and laboratory analysis

In order to perform geochemical and sedimentological analysis of Ria Formosa, 129 samples were collected from four (RF1, RF2, RF3 and RF4) and two (RFM21 and RFM59) sediment cores, obtained by mechanical and manual drilling respectively. Additionally, 28 surface samples were collected in the central part of the backbarrier environment of the system (Fig.1).

Mechanically drilled sediment cores were transported to the laboratory, split in two halves, photographed, macroscopically described in terms of stratigraphy, colour, textural class, sedimentary structures, visible organic matter (O.M.), and presence of bioclasts (Sousa et al., 2014; 2018). Sampling frequency for grain size and geochemical analysis was based on the chronostratigraphic model established by Sousa et al. (2018), following: (1) every 1cm to 30cm

in the units macroscopically characterized as fine fraction; (2) at every macroscopic facies change. Sub-sampling was performed in 1cm thick sub-samples. Manually drilled sediment cores were sampled in-situ applying the same methodology as with mechanically drilled sediment cores. All samples were (including surface samples) placed rapidly into plastic zip containers and freeze dried with a lyophilizer.

Figure 11 – Map of the Ria Formosa study area, with the location of surface samples (underlined numbers) and sediment cores. From the initial sampling plan, samples 7, 20, 21 and 22 were not collected.

Before analysis, two sub-samples were divided, one for grain-size study and the other for chemical analysis. Samples were subjected to O.M. destruction by addition of hydrogen peroxide (H_2O_2). Grain size distribution with visible coarser fraction was firstly analysed with mechanical sieve. The fine fraction was analysed using Malvern Mastersizer 2000 particle size analyser in a 500 ml solution of distilled water and hexametaphosphate antiflocculant.

The samples for metal analysis were grounded to $63\mu m$ with a mechanical agate mortar. Metal concentrations in the sediment samples ($n=129$ cores and $n= 28$ surface) were analysed by the accredited Bureau Veritas Mineral Laboratories Ltd. (Vancouver, Canada). Analytical procedure internal references were conducted according to AQ300 protocol (modified 1:1:1 $HNO_3:HCl:H_2O$ aqua regia digestion), following a similar approach to Delgado et al. (2010; 2012). Concentrations of 34 elements (major oxides and trace elements) were then determined by optical spectrometry

(ICP-ES). The results are expressed as $\mu\text{g}\cdot\text{g}^{-1}$ dry weight. This protocol method is considered suited to determine pseudototal metal content (McGrath and Cunliffe, 1985). The accuracy of measurements was checked using Bureau Veritas standard reference materials (STD DS10, STD OREAS45EA). Good agreement was obtained between the analysed and certified values.

3.2 Sediment Quality Assessment

In order to assess the impact of human activities in recent years in the Ria Formosa surface sediments the natural specific Bkd and EF were determined. The specific Bkd for each element in the Ria Formosa was determined based on palaeoenvironmental/ sedimentological interpretations. EF of the sediment was determined using following equation (Eq. 1):

$$EF = \frac{\left(\frac{[M]}{[N]}\right)_{sample}}{\left(\frac{[M]}{[N]}\right)_{background}} \quad (1)$$

Where:

$[M]_{sample}$ – metal M concentration for the studied sample

$[M]_{background}$ – regional background value for M

$[N]_{sample}$ – concentration of normalizing element for each metal sample

$[N]_{background}$ – value of normalizing element in the background

Aluminium was chosen as the normalizing element since it has the highest correlation between metals and the sediment clay fraction (e.g. Aloupi and Angelidis, 2001; Delgado et al., 2008). An EF value of 1 indicates a natural sediment origin for the element, while values greater than 1 indicate enrichment by natural processes (e.g. biota contributions) or anthropogenic influences (Zhang and Liu, 2002). EF values lower than 0.5 can reflect mobilization and loss of the element in relation to Al, or point out an overestimation of the background metal contents (Zhang et al., 1995).

EF distribution maps were generated by data interpolation using ESRI® ArcGIS® software Kernel Interpolation with Barriers geoprocessing tool. Details on the interpolation model used are discussed in Hoerl and Kennard (1970) and Gribov and Krivoruchko (2010). Interpolated surfaces used a 50m cell size grids (raster images). A maximum searching radius of 600 m is established for nearby samples (based on average minimum distance between two points and at least one interpolation point) in order to obtain a significant interpolated value spatial distribution for surrounding cells. Moreover, an interpolation barrier was used (maximum tidal reach) to avoid

separated samples interpolations. The Epanechnikov kernel function was selected, since it is expected to produce better results for first-order polynomials (Fan and Gijbels, 1996). As expected, uncertainty is inherent to any interpolation method, so the interpolation maps should be considered as possible expected values, but not necessarily the true values, which could never be obtained (e.g. Zhang, 2006).

4. Results and discussion

4.1 Subsurface samples geochemical characterization

Summary data for Al, Fe, As, Co, Cr, Cu, Ni, Pb and Zn elements analysed in six sediment cores, including their granulometric characteristics, are reported in Table 1 (complete data set available at Supplementary data).

Due to their elastic nature, the sediments are composed mainly of MnO_3 , Fe_2O_3 and Al_2O_3 , with mean values of 19.5, 2.8% and 1.5%, respectively. These are followed by CaO_3 (4.5%), K_2O (0.5%) and Na_2O (0.4%). The rest of the elements analysed are present at mean concentrations below 1%, except $S_{(total)}$, which present mean value of 1.7% indicating the redox condition of the sediments (Supplementary data).

The highest concentrations of trace elements are of Sr and V, whose mean values exceed 50 ppm (114.6 ppm and 51.2 ppm, respectively). These high values are associated with shell fragments in the case of Sr, or with heavy minerals derived from geochemical inputs associated with soil and bedrock erosion (Wu et al., 2007), which are very abundant in nearby SW-Iberia coastal sediments (Fernández-Caliani et al., 1997).

There are moderately elevated concentrations of elements that are considered potential contaminants, namely Zn, which shows a wide range of values between 10 and 97 ppm, with a mean of 37.9ppm (Table 1). Results for As and Cr also stand out, with a range of 2–70 and 14–79 ppm, and a mean value of 18.1 and 35.3 ppm, respectively. Other elements include Ni, Pb, Cu and Co with mean (and range) values of 23 (7–37), 14.8 (4–31), 14.4 (4–37) and 8.7 (3–21) ppm, respectively. Inversely, concentration values for 10 elements were not considered for being consistently below detection limit: Ag, Au, B, Bi, Cd, Ga, Hg, Sb, Sc and W. Between trace elements, Mo values are very high for living organisms. For this reason, we found very significant their mean concentrations of 4.6, with maximum values of 24 ppm. However, out of 129 analysed samples, 23 Mo values were bellow detection limit.

Table 1 - Descriptive statistics of Al, Fe, As, Co, Cr, Cu, Ni, Pb and Zn elements of the sediment cores analysed (aggregated values). Major elements are reported in %, trace in ppm. d.l. correspond to detection limits of the analyses.

		RF1 n=14				RF2 n=16				RF3 n=27				RF4 n=32				RFM21 n=25				RFM59 n=14			
		Mean	Max	Min	SD	Mean	Max	Min	SD	Mean	Max	Min	SD												
Clay	%	34.1	47.7	5.8	12.0	35.6	52.5	14.6	10.2	29.4	52.4	5.4	15.1	37.8	52.4	22.1	6.0	35.5	46.9	19.0	7.0	33.2	52.7	16.3	9.4
Silt	%	49.1	57.1	25.9	7.5	54.1	73.2	40.6	8.8	48.7	64.2	29.2	8.5	50.9	71.8	30.8	7.4	55.4	73.0	40.6	6.2	51.4	61.1	30.6	8.9
Sand	%	16.8	61.1	4.4	17.3	10.3	36.4	0.9	8.2	21.9	65.0	0.7	21.5	11.3	35.8	1.3	7.7	9.1	40.4	1.8	9.4	15.5	53.1	3.0	14.9
d.l.	Unit																								
Al	0.01 %	1.06	1.45	0.55	0.30	1.48	2.03	0.80	0.37	1.74	2.25	0.91	0.39	1.53	2.02	0.59	0.31	1.51	1.84	0.80	0.27	1.40	1.96	0.78	0.32
Fe	0.01 %	2.44	3.65	1.27	0.83	2.54	3.42	0.90	0.60	2.93	4.32	1.43	0.85	2.88	4.34	0.92	0.69	2.84	3.47	1.68	0.46	2.62	3.77	1.40	0.67
As	2 ppm	14.3	27.0	5.0	7.6	15.9	24.0	2.0	5.2	19.3	35.0	4.0	8.6	18.5	42.0	3.0	8.8	21.2	70.0	11.0	11.4	14.9	20.0	9.0	2.9
Co	1 ppm	7.4	11	4	2.3	7.8	13	4	2.4	9.4	21	5	3	9.9	19	3	2.9	8.5	12	4	2.3	7.6	13	3	2.8
Cr	1 ppm	27.3	39.0	14.0	8.8	31.9	43.0	15.0	7.1	35.9	48.0	20.0	8.8	38.5	79.0	14.0	10.5	38.4	51.0	24.0	6.6	33.4	46.0	18.0	8.3
Cu	1 ppm	11.7	18.0	6.0	4.0	14.4	23.0	8.0	4.6	14.6	20.0	8.0	3.3	15.8	37.0	4.0	5.4	14.5	20.0	7.0	3.7	12.9	24.0	4.0	4.6
Ni	1 ppm	19.1	27.0	10.0	5.8	22.6	33.0	12.0	6.2	24.4	34.0	13.0	5.4	24.6	37.0	8.0	5.8	24.0	33.0	13.0	5.1	19.3	30.0	7.0	6.2
Pb	3 ppm	10.8	15.0	5.0	3.0	16.2	31.0	6.0	6.2	19.4	28.0	8.0	5.2	14.3	23.0	6.0	4.2	14.4	22.0	6.0	4.5	10.4	18.0	4.0	4.4
Zn	1 ppm	30.5	45.0	15.0	10.3	38.4	53.0	21.0	10.0	41.1	86.0	17.0	14.4	38.3	97.0	11.0	14.0	40.9	54.0	22.0	7.7	31.7	42.0	10.0	9.2

4.2 Normalization of the geochemical data

The relationship between natural processes and the changes caused by human action on the geochemical availability of metals is an issue with many implications in various fields of knowledge. Subsequently, to properly compare the concentration of an element between samples, it is necessary to compensate for the effects of grain size by applying an appropriate correction (Aloupi and Angelidis, 2001). Since particle size is not the sole factor controlling elemental concentrations, many authors choose to normalise metal concentration using another element/component predominantly associated with the clay size-fraction (Lee and Cundy, 2001). Numerous conservative and normalising elements have been suggested in the bibliography such as Al, Cs and Fe: Al (i.e. Covelli et al., 2006), Li (Loring, 1991), Cs (Grousset et al., 1995) and Fe (i.e. Cobelo-García and Prego, 2003), and others, including Sc, grain size, and organic carbon. However, Fe and Al have been used most frequently as normalising elements, both in marine and estuarine sediments (Cundy and Croudace, 1996). This is because they are the principal constituents of the fine-grained aluminosilicates with which metals are frequently associated (Loring, 1991; Daskalakis and O'Connor, 1995). It adopts the normalization procedure of metal concentrations against the dominant conservative grain size proxy of the region and the calculation of EF with display of concentration scatterplots (Sabadini-Santos et al., 2009). To complete this aim, a Pearson's correlation coefficients study has been conducted. The data used for the analysis were Al, Fe, As, Co, Cr, Cu, Ni, Pb, Zn, since they have been described in numerous works as constituent elements associated with human activities in the SW of Iberia (e.g. Delgado et al., 2010). The coefficients obtained are represented in Table 2.

Table 2 - Pearson correlation matrix for the parameters analysed in the Ria Formosa. Alpha significant level 0.05. Number of samples, n = 129.

	Clay	Silt	Sand	Al	Fe	As	Co	Cr	Cu	Ni	Pb	Zn
Clay	1											
Silt	-0.46	1										
Sand	-0.73	-0.27	1									
Al	0.06	0.03	-0.09	1								
Fe	-0.17	0.21	0.03	0.76	1							
As	-0.08	0.05	0.06	0.44	0.61	1						
Co	-0.11	0.15	0.00	0.56	0.43	0.06	1					
Cr	-0.08	0.15	-0.02	0.73	0.75	0.48	0.57	1				
Cu	-0.05	0.09	-0.01	0.64	0.48	0.11	0.80	0.74	1			
Ni	-0.07	0.13	-0.03	0.80	0.67	0.33	0.84	0.79	0.88	1		
Pb	0.04	0.02	-0.07	0.70	0.49	0.41	0.28	0.49	0.46	0.51	1	
Zn	0.04	0.14	-0.15	0.73	0.59	0.50	0.34	0.61	0.53	0.63	0.65	1

In bold, significant values (except diagonal) at the level of significance alpha = 0.05 (two-tailed test). N=129.

Positive significant correlations with 95% confidence intervals were calculated for Al, Fe, and trace metals; R^2 (correlation) values obtained when normalised with Al were always higher (Table 2). Examples of these strong correlations with Al include Fe (0.76), Co (0.56), Cr (0.73), Cu (0.64), Ni (0.80), Pb (0.70) and Zn (0.73). Moderate correlations between Al and As (0.44) were found. The correlations revealed that Al is the most suitable conservative element for metal normalization procedures in the study area, indicating that they are locked up physically and/or chemically in detrital particles and minerals originating from an Al-rich lithogenic source.

4.3 Ria Formosa Background Value

The methods most commonly used to determine geochemical Bkd for metals are empirical geochemical methods (direct) or statistical (indirect) (Reimann et al., 2005; Rodríguez et al., 2006; Galuszka, 2007; de Paula et al., 2014). In this line, metal scatter plots depicted in Figure 2 for all core samples normalized against Al showing significant linear relationships of each metal and the 95% prediction limits, could reflect baseline conditions of the study area (Table 3). An insignificant number of outliers slightly beyond these limits was removed from the matrix for the calculation the middle regression equation (Fig. 2), defining the regional normalization functions useful for future environmental assessments of sediment quality (Sabadini-Santos et al., 2009). Baseline values in this study are as such estimated as the lowest 20% concentration values estimated in all core samples (Table 3), similar to Santos-Echeandía et al. (2012).

Table 3 – Baseline values (lowest 20%) and Background values (samples from Unit TF in cores RF1 and RF4) determined for Ria Formosa compared with other reported values in different sources.

	unit	Baseline [M] N=129			A	B	C	Background [M] N=27			Bkd [M/Al] N = 27	D
		Range	Mean					Range	Mean			
Al	%	0.6	1.2	0.9	0.97-78.2	0.46-9.20	0.27-2.16	0.8	2.0	1.5	1.0	18.2
Fe	%	0.9	2.2	1.7	-	-	-	1.9	3.7	2.9	1.9	7.0
As	ppm	2.0	12.0	8.3	-	-	-	3.0	42.0	16.5	11.0	17.5
Co	ppm	3.0	6.0	5.2	0.09-9.72	-	0.29-0.35	7.0	15.0	10.1	6.7	16.3
Cr	ppm	14.0	27.0	21.7	-	-	-	20.0	50.0	36.9	24.2	23.4
Cu	ppm	4.0	11.0	8.8	3.24-39.0	1.27-42.9	9.53-41.9	8.0	23.0	16.0	10.5	28.0
Ni	ppm	7.0	18.0	14.6	1.29-82.8	0.99-62.9	5.87-17.6	12.0	35.0	24.9	16.3	32.6
Pb	ppm	4.0	10.0	7.2	2.07-63.4	15.9-88.0	4.14-5.80	6.0	19.0	13.6	8.8	19.7
Zn	ppm	10.0	29.0	21.1	27.2-718	7.58-1099	16.3-62.1	19.0	58.0	36.6	24.0	76.4

A: Santos-Echeandía et al. (2012); B: (Laslett, 1995; Fileman et al., 1991); C: Kuss and Kremling (1999); D: Delgado et al. (2012).

However, baseline concepts include both the geogenic input (natural processes) and the concentration which results of anthropogenic activities inputs (Guillén et al., 2011). Although scatter plots similar to Figure 2 constitute a suitable reference tool for the recognition of future anthropogenic inputs, past metal content description on longer time scales for a given environment require other approaches.

Figure 2 - Relationship between Al and Fe, As, Cr, Co, Cu, Ni, Pb and Zn concentrations in core samples from the Ria Formosa. Middle lines represent the regression equation. Potentially anomalous concentrations lying outside the upper and lower lines, defined as $\pm 2\sigma$ range.

According to Delgado et al. (2012), combining M/Al ratios variations and lithological characteristics of sedimentary record could allow estimate the background metal concentrations from lithostratigraphic units that were unaffected by anthropogenic activities (local natural Bkd). Based on palaeoenvironmental-lithological interpretations (Sousa et al., 2018), we considered that

the Unit TF (-11 to -14.5m, core RF1; and -6.7 to -15.7m, core RF4) was indicative of pre-anthropogenic conditions. These sedimentary units are associated with a low intertidal depositional environment, related to backbarrier sheltered conditions with a quite homogeneous sedimentation. Also, according to the Depth/Age model proposed by Sousa et al. (2018) these units present estimated ages of 8500 cal yr BP to 7300 cal yr BP, where the natural metal fluxes prevail over the anthropogenic contributions (e.g. Delgado et al., 2012). For this reason, these units were chosen to obtain natural metal concentration levels or local Bkd (Table 3, N = 27).

4.4 Holocene geochemical record

Once local Bkd is identified, the extent of anthropogenic contamination by metals in a certain area (anomalies) can be obtained through the standardization of data by a conservative element and EF (Aprile and Bouvy, 2008; Hwang et al., 2009). Following Equation 1, anthropogenic input of metals is expected when the normalised concentration of the samples is higher than background levels (Hwang et al., 2009); i.e. when $EF > 1$.

If the EF variation is analysed on the basis of an Depth/Age model (Sousa et al., 2018), it is possible to obtain a long term observation (millennial scale) of metal concentration evolution in Ria Formosa, and also test the validity of the defined local Bkd (Fig. 3).

The EF profiles (Fig.3) show that practically during all time registered, elements as Fe, Co, Cr and Ni reached values close to the Bkd ($EF \sim 1$), displaying their essentially natural input. This behaviour is widely documented in the SW Iberia since Co, Cr and Ni are commonly part of the phyllosilicates that by surface alteration processes are formed in the basin, mobilized and transported to the estuary, where they tend to accumulate in the clay fraction of sediments (Borrego et al., 2004; Morillo et al., 2004; Delgado et al., 2010). It can be observed however that during the early Holocene until ca. 7500 cal yr BP elements as Co, Cr, Ni, Cu and Pb present significant fluctuations (RF1, RF3 and RF4 cores; Fig. 3). This period is characterized by a transition between fluvial to open estuarine sedimentation (Sousa et al., 2018). In fact, the transition from purely fluvial sedimentation to marine-fluvial mixed sedimentation, during the initial stage of the post-glacial estuarine sedimentary record of the Iberian Peninsula, is regionally marked by significant increase of Cr, Cu, Ni, and Zn concentration (Delgado et al., 2012).

Anthropogenic contributions to metal enrichment in Ria Formosa are only visible after ca. 7500 cal yr BP, with small increases of Pb in RF2, RF3 and RF4; and As in RF2 and RF4. This change can be associated mostly to the increased erosion resulting from a combination of the Holocene thermal climatic maximum (Azevêdo and Gonçalves, 2009), construction of fortifications and vine crops of the first settlements in the SW Iberia (Chapman, 2008), and selective deforestation (Delgado et al., 2012). Since the Neolithic (ca. 5800 cal yr BP) and mainly the Bronze Age (ca.

4500 cal yr BP) the earliest phase of agriculture and metallurgy has been recognised in Europe (Nocete et al., 2008; Thevenon et al., 2011), being associated to a clear increase of metals concentration in sediments, a process well documented in the Guadiana estuary (Delgado et al., 2012). In the Ria Formosa an evidence of this relationship can be observed mainly in the concentration increase of Pb (RF2); Pb, Zn (RF3); Cu, Pb, Zn (RF4); and Pb (RFM59). Finally, since the first millennium B.C. (ca. 3000 cal yr BP), the increase of Pb, Zn and As observed in the core RFM21 could reflect the stable settlement of the Tartessian Civilization in the SW of the Iberian Peninsula, where in this period, coinciding with another climate optimum (after Dansgaard et al., 1969 and Schönwiese, 1995), increases of lithogenic element concentrations as Co, Cr and Ni (namely As in RFM21), could be associated with the proliferation of civilizations (Delgado et al., 2012).

Figure 3 – EF vertical profiles for As, Co, Cr, Cu, Fe, Ni, Pb and Zn in Ria Formosa sediment cores, showing the behaviour of the elements in the Holocene sedimentary record based on the Depth/Age model of Sousa et al. (2018).

Considering the local baseline range and Bkd inferred in this study and comparing with the baseline reported by Santos-Echeandía et al. (2012) for Portuguese coast, our upper values and mean distribution are lower than the upper limit proposed for all elements (Table 3). However, the lower limits for Cu and Pb are very close to Santos-Echeandía et al. (2012), while the lower values obtained to Co and Ni surpassed it. This effect is probably due to the differences in the measured scenarios between this study (estuarine sediments) and the values of Santos-Echeandía et al. (2012), particulate matter that principally contributes metal to the sediments. Regarding the results, we find a similar scenario, with similar levels between this study and other European coastal or open ocean waters of the North Sea (Laslett, 1995; Fileman et al., 1991) and North Atlantic (Kuss and Kremling, 1999), verifying that in all cases our mean baseline and Bkd are framed between the respective limits stabilised by these authors.

On the other hand, the established local Bkd values are similar when compared with the results obtained by Delgado et al. (2012) from the Guadiana estuary, closely located to the study area in the SW Iberia. Overall, the results obtained in this study for Al, Fe, Cu, Pb and Zn, elements frequently associated with the Acid Mine Drainage (AMD) generated in the inner drainage zones of the Iberian Pyrite Belt, SW Iberia, (e.g. Sarmiento et al., 2004; Cánovas et al., 2007; Delgado et al., 2009) are smaller than the results obtained by Delgado et al. (2012), due to the restricted watershed of Ria Formosa and as such evidencing the negligible AMD in this system. Nevertheless, Cr reports values very similar to those found in Guadiana estuary sediments during the last 4500 cal yr BP (Delgado et al., 2012), probably reflecting a high natural source of this metal in the region.

4.5 Present-day metal contamination

With a local Bkd available, it is possible to accurately determine if a particular metal has been enriched (Liu et al., 2002), information that can provide an objective basis for decision making by public officials and for the proper use of natural resources (de Paula et al., 2014).

In order to better assess the present status of the Ria Formosa potential metal contamination, three different datasets were used to create distribution maps of metal contaminants with a GIS-analysis (Fig. 4). These maps are useful for the identification of potential contamination inputs from different sources into the system, thus creating better management options of an environmentally sensitive area. They can also prove to be a reliable tool that facilitates coastal systems monitoring (e.g. Chica-Olmo et al., 2004).

In the left column, interpolated distribution maps of surface sediment metal content values are presented. Metal content values are Al-normalized (see section 4.2) and represented in a 5-colour gradient defined from the obtained minimum value with standard deviation increments until the

maximum value. In the middle column, metal EF distribution maps are presented, estimated from Equation 1 and based on the Ria Formosa Bkd value (see section 4.3). Lastly, in the right column, distribution maps of dredged material classification (5 classes) are presented, following the Portuguese Ordinance 1450 (2007) sediments contamination levels. In this classification system, Class 1 sediments are considered as clean, with no contamination, while Class 2 sediments present vestigial contamination, where attention to final deposition must be considered. In Ordinance 1450 (2007), values are only defined for As, Cd, Cr, Cu, Hg, Pb, Ni, Zn.

Figure 4 – From left to right columns: M/Al sediment content (in ppm); EF value; Dredged sediment Class (Ordinance 1450, 2008); distribution maps for As, Cu, Pb and Zn (respectively in lines). Circled letters locate potential contamination sources: A – WWTP; B – Boat repair dock; C – Mooring area; D – Industrial area; E – Aquaculture.

Results in Figure 4 considered the regulated metals in Ordinance 1450 (2007), the Directive on Environmental Quality Standards of European Union (Directive 2008/105/EC), that defines Ni, Cd, Pb and Hg as priority substances among metals, and Commission Regulation (EC) no.1881/2006 that sets the maximum metal levels in edible bivalve molluscs for Pb, Cd and Hg. As such, we only included As, Cr, Cu, Ni, Pb, and Zn in the GIS analysis. Hg and Cd were excluded for being below detection limit in the samples collected in the sediment cores, thus without an estimated local Bkd value. Cr and Ni are not represented in Figure 4 for obtained results show EF values very close to 1 in all samples (average 1.2 and 0.91 respectively), thus pointing to a solely lithogenic origin in the system, being negligible the anthropic contribution.

The remaining analysed metals: As, Cu, Pb and Zn; all present a specific distribution in the study area and are explained hereafter.

As surface concentration values were unexpectedly high when compared to other studies (Valença et al., 2012; Botelho et al., 2017). In the study area, normalized As mean value is 18.5 ppm (SD = 6.4) with minimum and maximum values of 9.2 and 40.7 ppm, respectively. These high surface values result in a considerable area with Class 2 sediments (Ordinance 1450, 2007) (Fig. 4, As-Class). However, EF values are generally low, with a mean value of 1.7, contrasting with a single higher anomaly detected south of the Faro Airport where EF = 3.7 (Fig. 4, As-EF), evidencing a contamination source of probable anthropic origin. Sewage inputs are of little significance in terms of As contamination (Bryan and Langston, 1992), where obtained results corroborate the inexistence of enrichment close to potential contamination sources (Fig. 4). Although the vast majority of As contamination results from wood preservatives, agricultural chemicals, and the production of glass (Bryan and Langston, 1992), in Ria Formosa no source of such types can be clearly identified. Reflecting the low EF values, the As content in Ria Formosa subsurface sediments (see section 4.3) can prove to be a significant source, where diagenetic cycling of As is considered responsible for higher values observed in estuarine sediments (Bryan and Langston, 1992).

Cu distribution presents higher values in the proximity of Faro and south of Faro Airport (Fig. 4 Cu/Al). As expected, Cu EF values follow the same distribution (Fig. 4, Cu-EF). Cu has an EF mean value of 2.2 (SD = 1.66), with minimum and maximum values of 1 and 9.4 respectively. Nonetheless, if the four samples with higher EF are excluded, mean value is 1.6 (SD = 0.3) for the remaining area, thus understood as with no relevant anthropic influence (Fig. 4, Cu-EF). Dredged sediments classification map also reflects the EF distribution (Fig. 4 Cu-Class), indicative of the natural system disturbance in higher Cu concentration areas. Cortesão et al. (1986) and Valença et al. (2012) also observed higher Cu values in the proximity of urban areas. Cu is considered to be incorporated in suspended particulate matter, associated to higher O.M. contents deriving from sewage runoff (Cortesão et al., 1986), and rapidly remobilized to the water column (Benoliel et al., 1988, Caetano et al., 2002). However, samples collected close to a Wastewater Treatment Plant (WWTP) (Fig. 4, source A) do not prove to be point sources of contamination. Thus, significant sources of Cu must be related to diffuse sources, such as release from metallic structures and antifouling paints, or incorporated in O.M. present in untreated urban discharges (Bryan and Langston, 1992), and to some extent, resulting from aquaculture practices (Botelho et al., 2017) (Fig. 4, source E).

Similarly, Pb is mostly concentrated in the surroundings of Faro urban area (Fig. 4 Pb/Al), where values exceed the 30 ppm threshold, with a critical enhancement close the pluvial water drain of

the Faro industrial area (75 ppm). Pb presence is often associated to petrol additives used in boats (Bryan and Langston, 1992; Bebianno, 1995), concentrating in areas with more marine traffic (Fig. 4, sources B and C) and in the drainage area of the Faro industrial area, a former fuel deposit (Fig. 4, source D). In all the study area, Pb presents a generalized high EF, indicative of significant anthropic influence (Fig. 4, Pb-EF), a result also observed by Valença et al. (2012) and Cortesão et al. (1986). The EF mean value is of 2.7 (SD = 1.4), with a minimum of 1.7 in the salt farms of Ludo (Fig. 1) and a maximum of 8.7 in Faro industrial area. However, according to dredged sediments classification (Ordinance 1450, 2007), with the one exception (Fig. 4 Pb-Class), the study area is considered to be uncontaminated, where the Class 2 limit is established for values greater than 50 ppm.

Finally, Zn is identified as the most abundant metal contaminant in Ria Formosa (Cortesão et al., 1986; Valença et al., 2012; Botelho et al., 2017). Obtained results show an Al-normalized mean value of 83 ppm in the study area, with peak values of 270 ppm in the Faro industrial area vicinity (Fig. 4, Zn/Al, source D). EF results are also indicative of the significant enrichment resulting from anthropic influence, with a mean value of 3.4 (SD = 2.2), and minimum and maximum values of 1.4 and 11.2, respectively, the highest among the analysed metals. However, dredged sediments classification map (Fig. 4 Zn-Class) does not reflect the EF distribution greater than 3 (Fig. 4 Zn-EF), resulting from anthropic activities enrichment. Although the study area is clearly enriched in relation to the Ria Formosa Bkd value, the Ordinance 1450 (2007) Class 2 limit for Zn is 100 ppm, therefore resulting in only two specific areas identified as with vestigial contamination (Fig. 4 Zn-Class). Zn sources to the system can be related to industrial discharges, rubber materials, and release from metallic structures (Bryan and Langston, 1992), where zinc plating processing units, known to exist upstream the Lavadeiras tributary (Fig.1), are the most probable source in that area.

Although considered largely unpolluted when compared to other systems (e.g. Blasco et al., 2010; Valença et al., 2012), the central section of Ria Formosa lagoon presents significant metal enrichment. EF determination for the study area highlighted the differences between Ordinance 1450 (2007) limits for Class 2 sediments and metal enrichment considering the local Ria Formosa Bkd. While As shows a good correlation, where EF values greater than 2 correspond to Class 2 sediments, the remaining metals have higher thresholds. Cu in sediments only changes to Class 2 with $EF > 3$, Zn with $EF > 4$, and Pb only with $EF > 6$, leading to question the meaning of such differences. The identification of contamination sources to the study area is also made possible with Figure 4. Small tributaries and WWTP contribution to metal enrichment have a negligible impact in the study area, with overall low sediment metal concentration values and near 1 EF values close to discharge areas (Fig.1 and Fig.4). Diffuse contamination, namely resulting from pluvial water drains near the major urban areas, appears to be the most significant source of metals

to the system. Seasonal variation, with enhanced values resulting from higher rain runoff (Bebianno, 1995; Botelho et al., 2017), particularly in the proximity of anthropogenic sources (Caetano et al., 2002), further emphasizes the importance of diffusive sources for the accumulation of metals in Ria Formosa.

5. Conclusions

This study presents for the first time a description of metal concentration evolution in Ria Formosa during the Holocene. Analysed metal content in the subsurface points to a similar behaviour in all cores, although results do not permit to isolate past significant inputs of allochthonous origin (anthropic effect) to the system. However, by combining the Holocene geomorphological evolution description it is possible to identify pre-anthropogenic sedimentary units, selected for the definition of the local Bkd values. The selected method for local Bkd determination was significantly accurate, producing very few EF values lower than 0.5. At a millennial timescale, Ria Formosa is considered to be a largely undisturbed system with reduced evidence of anthropogenic metal contamination.

Also, this study allowed us to apply local Bkd values in the analysis of present-day metal contamination in surface sediments in Ria Formosa. EF calculation considering the local Bkd values produces more accurate results in terms of environmental quality assessment, determining if a selected metal concentration is due to natural processes, or resulting from anthropogenic contamination. The combination of GIS analysis tools further increases the validity of this method, locating in the Ria Formosa areas that require further analysis in order to better identify potential contamination sources, where As and Zn, and to some extent Cu and Pb, are of special concern.

Finally, obtained present-day results are considered complementary to metal contamination evaluation approaches based on pre-established ranges, showing that high EF values are not systematically related to higher contamination classifications.

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